

AESOP IS THE FOUNDER OF THE FABLE GENRE

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Abstract: In this article, the stages of importance of the "parable" as a literary genre, which is considered one of the directions of the literary creator Aesop, are theoretically covered. The conducted scientific research shows that the genre of the parable has mainly moral, educational and didactic influence, and it was widely used in the pedagogic activities of the European countries in the 16th century. Later, the parable's beautiful simile potential and allegorical power were used as a protest against the oppression of the ruling powers.

Key words: parable, literary genre, Aesop's method, intellectual spear, epic of animals, poetic parables, cryptography, fabulist, allegory, paraphrase

There is a traditional allegorical method in literature. In addition, there is cryptography, the method of using allegories to deliberately mask the author's thought, his idea, which can be called "deceptive tools". The authors created in their works using allegory, irony, paraphrase, "legendary characters", nicknames with transparent context. In particular, allegory is one of the main expressive methods of the parable genre.

Aesop is considered the founder of the fable genre in the world. He was the slave of Aesop, a semi-legendary figure of ancient Greek literature, who lived on the island of Samos. He is said to have been killed by the Delphians on the orders of Amasis, the king of Egypt who lived between 570 and 526 BC. There is no scientific information about Aesop's life now. At that time, the term "Aesopian language" appeared. Aesop was called a "fabulist". More than a hundred years later, Aesop of the Heraclides of Pontus is said to have come from Thrace, to have been a contemporary of Pericles, and to have had Xanthus as his first master, but he derives this information from Herodotus' story by unreliable deductions. Plato, a comedian who lived at the end of the 5th century, mentioned the reincarnation of Aesop after his death. Alexis, the comedian who wrote Aesop's Comedy, pits his character against Solon, who had already woven Aesop's fables into the fables of the Seven Wise Men and King Croesus. His contemporary Lysippos also knew this version. He describes Aesop at the beginning of the seven sages. Xanthus' slavery, his relationship with the seven wise men, and his death at the hands of the Delphic priests were all developed by the end of the fourth century. Then they became links to Aesopian legend. Aesop's historicity was not doubted in the literature of Antiquity BC, and those

who emphasized Aesop's legend with a decisive characteristic characteristic of the hypercriticism of his time. By the end of the 5th century, during the time of Aristophanes, there is information that a written collection of Aesop's fables was known in Athens. Children learned it at school. Accordingly, "You are an ignorant and lazy person, you haven't even studied Aesop, " says one character of Aristophanes. It can be seen that the heroes of Aesop's works are the characters who initiate virtue and goodness and become an example for others. These were prosaic repetitions without any artistic exaggeration. In fact, the so-called "Aesop collection" includes fables from different eras. Aesop's name later became a symbol. His works were passed down by word of mouth, and his name is mentioned in 10 books of Demetrius of Faler, who lived in the IV century BC. This collection disappeared after the 9th century. During the reign of Emperor Augustus, Phaedrus translated these legends into Latin verse, and Avian translated 42 legends into Latin around the 10th century. Around 200 AD, Babri described them in Greek verses. Babri's works were included by Planud (1260-1310) in his famous collection, which later influenced the fabulists. All of Aesop's Fables were composed in the Middle Ages. Later, the interest in Aesop's fables turned into an interest in his personality. Due to the lack of reliable information about him, those who were interested turned to legends related to his name. For example, the Phrygian interlocutor satirizes the mighty power of this world. Homer's Thersites appears to be a quarrelsome and angry person, and therefore the portrait of Thersites, detailed by Homer, is also copied into Aesop. He was not left out of consideration in sculpture, and at the same time, he was depicted as an interesting statue that has reached us. A biography of Aesop was written in Byzantium in the Middle Ages, and it has long been accepted as a reliable source of information about Aesop. Aesop is represented here as a slave, sold from hand to hand for a pittance. He is always upset with his colleagues, supervisors and bosses, but always thinks of taking revenge on the criminals around him. This biography is not only a true biography of Aesop, but also not based on Greek legends about him. Martin Luther finds that Aesop's Fables is not a single work of a single author, but a collection of old and new fables, and that the traditional image of Aesop is the fruit of a "poetic fable."

Aesop's fables have been translated into many languages of the world and many have been revised, including the famous fabulists Jean de La Fontaine and Ivan Krylov, who have used many of his fables and fables in their works. A complete translation of all Aesop's fables in Russian was published in 1968.

By the 20th century, attempts were made to estimate the historical prototype of Aesop's image again. A collection of 426 short fables under the name of Aesop was collected and found to have been preserved in prose. Aesop (Áisopos) is recognized as the creator of the fable. In legends, Aesop is depicted as a folk sage, thrown from a cliff in the form of a lame slave.

are based on folk tales with a long history . Aesop's fables are often vivid everyday scenes from folk life, and they are a prime example of early fiction. Later, the legacy of Aesop was corrupted, modified and imitated, and it was repeated by the Roman fabulist Phaedrus and the Greek fabulist Babri until the poetic adaptations of La Fontaine, Dmitriev, Izmailov and others. Essayist Martin Luther, translator of ancient, medieval and modern poetry and prose in European poetry : "Aesop's fables is not a single work of a single author, but a collection of old and new narratives, and the traditional image of Aesop is "poetic considered the "fruit" of the legend.

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